

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
California State University, Los Angeles

SCHOOL NURSE-LED INTERVENTION FOR HEALTH-RELATED CHRONIC
ABSENTEEISM

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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May 2023

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DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10548177
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ABSTRACT

School absenteeism leads to poor performance in school and reduced future health and socioeconomic outcomes. School nurses use their education and expertise to recognize and intervene in health-related problems affecting the learning environment. With a school nurse-led absence surveillance initiative, at-risk students can be identified early, families can be connected to appropriate resources, and students can be more closely monitored to determine the effectiveness of interventions and improved attendance. This project aimed to adapt and implement a process to consistently identify students with cluster health-related chronic absences using the NASN School Nurse-Led Active Surveillance Manual and document and evaluate the effectiveness of school nurse intervention. The Iowa Model and 21st Century Framework for School Nursing Practice™ guided this project. Attendance data was collected for first-semester students of the 2022-23 school year and compared to first-semester students of the 2019-20 school year to evaluate if students with cluster health-related absences were identified and referred to the school nurse. In 2022-23, 233 students were eligible for referral based on the developed criteria, and 58 students were referred to the school nurse for cluster health-related absences compared to the 2019-20 school year, with 165 students eligible for referral and four students referred. Following the Active Surveillance Manual NASN toolkit steps, all students with cluster health-related absences received outreach to determine the need for support to return to school. A standard operating procedure was developed for the attendance clerk, school nurse, teachers, and administrators to improve consistency and accuracy of documentation, monitoring, and referral of chronically absent students. The project's overall goal was to ensure accurate documentation, tracking, reporting, and follow-up for students with cluster health-related absences and identify students at higher risk of illness or injury to provide additional support or accommodations that allowed them to return to school.

Keywords: school nurse, absence, chronic absence, absenteeism, school absenteeism, truancy, illness-related absence, case management

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would have never started this program or completed this project if it were not for the support of my Foster Five, Bill, Joel, Julie, Sarah, and Claire! Each of you makes life better in every way. You have all inspired me to grow and keep going even when the program became hard. I appreciate all your sacrifices along the journey. Each of you are the reason I continued to show up and give my best daily. I am proud to be your wife and mother!

My deepest appreciation to Dr. McClanahan, my team leader and cheerleader, as I embarked on this journey. You have provided patience, wisdom, encouraging words and leadership every step of the way. You believed in me when I was uncertain if I should continue down this path. To my committee member, Dr. Weismuller, thank you for your expertise and comments on my project as I progressed through the program and the project.

To my district leadership team and coworkers, not once did any of you complain when I was not around on a Friday, even in the thick of COVID. My coworkers picked up the slack and got the job done in my absence. Without your support, I would not have been able to complete this project. It is my hope this program enriches my practice as a school nurse so I can more greatly serve our school district and students daily.

A special thanks to 6G1GQI! Each of you provided a level of richness to this journey that was unimaginable. The support 6G1GQI offered helped to keep me grounded and headed in the right direction. Whether knowledge checks, class preps or group projects, each of you made every step of the way more fun and meaningful. Our group was truly the best group!

Background

School absenteeism leads to poor performance in school and has negative social effects and reduced adult health and socioeconomic outcomes (Allison & Attisha, 2019; Gottfried, 2014; Lim et al., 2019; McKinley-Yoder, 2017; Rankine et al., 2021; Schroder et al., 2021). California Education Code 48205 establishes a legal requirement for students to attend school every day, allowing absences to be excused for religious holidays, bereavement, quarantine, illness, medical appointments, or court appearances (California Legislative Information, 2022). Chronic absenteeism, defined as having missed at least 10% of the school year or greater than two days per month, results from excused and unexcused absences (Rankine et al., 2021; Schroder et al., 2021). Unlike chronic absenteeism, truancy is defined as a student's willful absence from school (Allison et al., 2019). School nurses are concerned about students with health-related chronic absences.

The school district of interest has an average enrollment of 11,000 students in Transitional Kindergarten through 12th grade at 14 sites. Within the district, 12.1% of students qualify for free and reduced lunch, and 5.6% are classified as English Language Learners. Free and reduced lunch indirectly measures the number of students living in poverty. The district employs 3.3 full-time equivalent school nurses covering four to six different school sites. In the 2018-19 school year, the nationwide average for chronic absenteeism was 12.9% (Lannan, 2021). The California average for the same school year was 9% (California Department of Education [CDE], 2017.). That year, in the western part of Los Angeles County, the school district of interest had 5.6% of the entire student body absent greater than 10% of the school year, representing more than 600 of the 11,000 students enrolled (CDE, 2017.). Although this

average is lower than that of the nation and the state, chronic absenteeism must be addressed to ensure student success.

The district of interest utilizes a three-step process to address excessive absences. However, the process is not implemented consistently throughout the district. In addition, the school sites do not consistently involve the school nurse in the initial phases of the process. After six unexcused absences, families receive a letter detailing actions that may be taken if attendance does not improve. This letter also instructs parents to contact the school attendance clerk if absences are related to chronic medical conditions. When unexcused absences reach nine, a second letter is sent home, and a Student Success Team (SST) meeting is held to break the cycle. The SST meeting, which includes the school-site administrator, classroom teacher, and school counselor, focuses on addressing individual attendance needs with the potential for developing an attendance contract between parent, student, and the school site. If the school-site administrator feels absences are related to a medical condition, a school nurse will be invited to the SST meeting. Finally, after 12 unexcused absences, a third letter is sent home, and a Student Attendance Review Board (SARB) meeting is scheduled. For children 6-18 years of age, school attendance is compulsory. The goal of the SARB is to keep students in school and ensure they have a meaningful education. SARB carries the power to refer students and their families to court (CDE, 2022). SARB meeting is convened with an independent panel of district, county, and community participants and can result in a referral to a probation officer or the district attorney. The independent panel consists of a district attorney's office representative, social services, Sheriff's deputy, school nurse, and an administrative SARB chair (Las Virgenes Unified School District, 2019)

School Nurse Role and Impact

School nurses use their education and expertise to recognize and intervene in health-related problems affecting the learning environment (Rankine et al., 2021; Schroder et al., 2018). School nurses provide care coordination, hands-on health care for acute and chronic health conditions, vision, and hearing screenings, develop health plans, train staff, perform preventative health screenings, and present health education (National Association of School Nursing [NASN], 2023). The school nurse facilitates the identification of students who are at greatest risk for chronic absenteeism (Darnell et al., 2019; NASN, 2020b, Paulson et al., 2021; Schroder et al., 2021). Through a trusted partnership with families and school staff, school nurses plan and implement actions to increase the attendance of identified at risk students (Schroder et al., 2018).

Early dismissals and absenteeism are lost class time for students. When evaluated by a school nurse, early dismissals are less common, and students are less likely to leave school early compared to evaluations by unlicensed personnel (McKinley-Yoder, 2017). Regardless of the reason the student is evaluated by the school nurse, students are more likely to return to class than leave school early (Allison et al., 2019; Schroder et al., 2018).

Statement of the Problem

Social determinants of health (SDOH), the conditions in which people are born, grow, live, work, and learn, can significantly impact an individual's health (Schroeder et al., 2018). Healthy People 2030 lists lack of access to education as a component of SDOH (Office of Disease Prevention and Health Promotion, n.d.). Students who have access to education by regularly attending school have a better opportunity to participate in their education, get good grades, graduate, and go to college or gain employment. There is ample research demonstrating the positive influence of graduating from high school on individual health and wealth (Darnell et

al., 2019; Schroder et al., 2021). High school graduates report a lower level of diabetes and heart disease, and the more years of education an individual has, the higher their earning potential (Darnell et al., 2019; Schroder et al., 2021).

Due to their accessibility to children and families, assessment and interventions by school nurses can play a crucial role in decreasing absenteeism among students of all grades, and as the only healthcare providers in schools, school nurses are well-positioned to address SDOH, specifically, access to education (Rankine et al., 2021; Schroeder et al., 2018; Weismuller et al., 2007). However, they are underutilized in this area of their expertise. Therefore, a standardized approach to addressing chronic absenteeism should include school nurse expertise and involvement. By using a school nurse-led initiative, at-risk students can be identified early, families are connected to appropriate resources, and students can be more closely monitored to determine whether the interventions have been successful (NASN, 2020b). When a school culture supports school nurse-led initiatives, nurses can get buy-in from school staff, bring visibility to the school nurse role, and improve revenue for schools whose funding is based on student attendance (NASN, 2020b; Rankine et al., 2021). As school nurses address the SDOH, including access to education, the potential for dropping out of high school decreases (McKinley-Yoder, 2017).

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this project is to develop and implement a process to consistently identify students who have health-related chronic absences, notify school nurses of students who have health-related chronic absences for follow-up using the NASN School Nurse-Led Active Surveillance Manual, and document and evaluate effectiveness of school nurse intervention.

Supporting Framework

A framework is a map that provides direction to take a clinical problem and identify the intervention, resulting in organizational change (Brown, 2014). The Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice (Appendix E; Figure 1) is a heuristic model developed by nurses to guide evidence-based practice (EBP) and infuse change (Buckwalter et al., 2017). The Iowa Model was first introduced in 1994 and used widely in academic settings and healthcare institutions (Brown, 2014; Titler et al., 2001). The most recent version, the Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care, is a seven-step process with three decision points to guide the user through undertaking an EBP project from the point of identifying a triggering issue through identification pilot testing the change and dissemination of results (Iowa Model Collaborative et al., 2017).

Triggering Issue, Opportunity

The revised model starts with identifying triggering issues or opportunities, emphasizing patient and family values (Buckwalter et al., 2017). These triggers are catalysts for nurses to look critically at their efficiencies and seek evidence-based knowledge for improvement (Titler et al., 2001). Other opportunities to infuse EBP change based on the revised model include new evidence, accrediting agency requirements, regulations, and philosophy of care (Buckwalter et al., 2017; Iowa Model Collaborative et al., 2017). For this DNP project, the triggering issue is increased absenteeism among students in a public school district in Los Angeles County.

Clinical Problem and Purpose

The second step in the Iowa Model is to identify a clinical problem and develop a clinical question. The clinical problem identified for this project is that the district of interest does not utilize a standardized approach for involving the school nurse to help manage chronic

absenteeism. This gap creates an opportunity to standardize a process to identify chronically absent students. The proposed intervention standardizes the process and implements inclusion of the school nurse utilizing The School Nurse-Led Active Surveillance Manual. This manual is an eight-step evidenced-based intervention that lays out the steps to intervene and outreach to students who suffer from chronic health-related absences (NASN, 2020b). Implementing these activities will ensure inclusion of key administrators and staff, lead to early identification of at-risk students, connect families to appropriate resources, and monitor students more closely to determine the success of interventions. The first decision point in the Iowa Model is to determine if the identified problem is a priority for the institution. This project aligns with the district's priorities, whose mission, in part, is to ensure programs are dedicated to enhancing student success. Alignment of these priorities allows progression through the framework to form a team.

Team Formation

The formation of the team should involve interprofessional members with the skills needed to plan, conduct, and evaluate the process (Buckwalter et al., 2017; Iowa Model Collaborative et al., 2017). The multidisciplinary team will consist of the Assistant Superintendent of Education Services, Secondary Principal, Attendance Clerk, Health Clerk, District Student Data Specialist, a school nurse, and the author, a practicing district school nurse. The Assistant Superintendent of Education is the chair of the SARB Committee and has vast knowledge regarding district attendance processes and education codes. Including a secondary principal, attendance clerk, and health clerk helps to create buy-in at the site level. The health clerk and attendance clerk will help identify students who leave early due to acute or chronic illness, provide administrative support, and identify students with increased health-related absences. The district student data specialist will provide data support.

Assemble, Appraise, and Synthesize Evidence

The Iowa Model Revised incorporates assembling, appraising, and synthesizing the literature within one step (Buckwalter et al., 2017). The purpose of the literature review is to conduct a thorough systematic search that covers multiple aspects of the topic, establishes the author as the expert, and represents work that has previously been done (Bonnell & Smith, 2018). Appraisal and synthesis of the literature will allow for evaluating the overall quality of the literature available and drawing conclusions from the findings (Bonnell & Smith, 2018; Roush, 2019). After synthesizing the literature, the Iowa Model presents another decision point. The second decision point in the Iowa Model involves determining if the literature review results support the proposed practice change. Once compelling evidence to support the change has been established, the model guides the team to the next step, which is designing and pilot testing the proposed change.

Design and Pilot the Practice Change

The Iowa Model guides the team to design the practice change before final adoption (Buckwalter et al., 2017 & Titler et al., 2001). Implementation of The School Nurse-Led Active Surveillance Manual will begin with standardization of the attendance tracking process at the school site. In partnership with the principal, the author will begin by ensuring the school site will notify the school nurse of all health-related absences. Additionally, the school nurse will look at current local policy surrounding health-related absences and ensure consistent protocol is followed, e.g., including a review of the automated tracking system to include the reason for absence, doctor's notes if more than three days of school is missed and report of communicable diseases to school within 24 hours of diagnosis.

Following standardization of the attendance tracking system, families will be alerted, through a legal handbook, that when their student misses more than two days a month, the school nurse will reach out to families. The school attendance clerk will alert the school nurse when a student has two or more health-related absences in one month. For those absences, the school nurse will reach out to families to determine the reasons for their absence and assess the need for resources. Assessment of the student's medical situation will result in follow-up with these students and their families and will include developing a plan for the student to return to school (NASN, 2020b).

Before pilot testing the proposed change, a plan for a phased approach for implementation, including staff education and preparation of resources, will be developed. Data will drive the pilot test to determine the effectiveness of the practice change. After the piloting phase, as per the Iowa Model, the final decision point is to determine if the change can appropriately be adopted.

Integrate and Sustain the Change

If it is determined that the school nurse-led initiative is decreasing chronic absenteeism, the initiative can be integrated at additional schools. Data collected in the pilot phase will be shared with the multidisciplinary team, superintendent, and school board. Dissemination of results will help to promote change district-wide. In addition to the school board, the practice change will be shared with other principals in the district of interest to promote permanent change in school attendance procedures. Attendance data will be monitored at each school site. Monitoring of the process will measure the effectiveness of the surveillance. Sustaining change requires continued monitoring (Buckwalter et al., 2017).

Dissemination

Doctoral-prepared nurses should disseminate their knowledge to multidisciplinary colleagues and policymakers through publication and other formats (Hanrahan et al., 2010). Sharing this project will help other school nurses to evaluate their local attendance practice and use the evidence to facilitate change. This project will be shared at the project's culmination through a poster presentation at scientific meetings at the local and regional levels. A manuscript will be developed for potential publication in a nursing specialty journal.

Integration with 21st Century Framework for School Nursing Practice™

The NASN Framework for 21st Century School Nursing Practice™ (Appendix F; Figure 2), developed to help guide school nursing practice, will be integrated into this project. The Framework focuses on the student, who is surrounded by the family and school community (NASN, 2020a). The framework has five nonhierarchical principles: care coordination, community/public health, leadership, quality improvement, and standards of practice (NASN, 2020a). These five principles provide an umbrella under which school nurse activities come together (NASN, 2020a). The framework's focus aligns with the patient-centered focus of the Iowa Model (NASN, 2020a). Utilizing the Iowa Model for this project helps the author integrate EBP within the school community. EBP is the standard of care for the 21st-century school nurse (NASN, 2020a). Students have complex health needs, and the school nurse has the knowledge and ability to integrate EBP. Within the care coordination principle, the school nurse utilizes evidence-based interventions to address a variety of social, mental, and health concerns to ensure student access to the classroom and decrease health-related absences (NASN, 2020a). By applying community and public health principles, school nurses promote a healthy environment and outreach to families to decrease absenteeism (NASN, 2020a). Quality improvement is an

ongoing principle that strives for consistent improvement and growth (NASN, 2020a).

Promotion of meaningful health and improved academic outcomes leads the school nurse to involvement and follow for health-related absences (NASN, 2020b). Integrating NASN's Framework for 21st Century School Nursing Practice™ will help focus and guide the project process and into a meaningful project to help students maximize their well-being and academic success.

Review of Literature

Overview

The purpose of this project is to develop and implement a process to consistently identify students who have health-related chronic absences, notify school nurses of students who have health-related chronic absences for follow-up using the NASN School Nurse-Led Active Surveillance Manual, and document and evaluate effectiveness of school nurse intervention. A literature review was conducted in preparation for this DNP project. Relevant articles were sought using PubMed, CINAHL, APA Psycinfo, ERIC, and Education Full-Text databases. Search terms included school health nursing, school nurse, intervention, educational attainment, academic achievement, and absenteeism. The search was limited to English-language articles published between 2012 and 2022. Articles addressing absenteeism for ages 5-18 are included. The search yielded 118 articles. Inclusion criteria included peer-reviewed journals and articles addressing absenteeism in children between 5-18 years of age. Thirteen duplicate articles were removed from the searches. A total of 36 articles were reviewed. The reference lists of relevant articles were searched to identify additional articles. This search method yielded three additional articles, which were included despite their publication date falling outside the original inclusion window.

The literature search was focused on articles related to the effects of chronic absenteeism on educational attainment and the impact the school nurse can have on decreasing absenteeism. The literature was also reviewed for articles on social determinants of health, school nurse interventions, workload, and impact on students with chronic health conditions. A search for standardized processes and nursing diagnoses was also performed.

What is Absenteeism?

An absence occurs when a student does not attend school regardless of the reason (Gentle-Genitty & Renguette, 2020). Chronic absenteeism is defined as having missed at least 10% of the school year or more than two days per month due to excused and unexcused absences (Attendance Works, 2018; Rankine et al., 2021; Schroder et al., 2021). The concept of chronic absence was introduced in 2006 through the publication *Present, Engaged and Accounted for: The Critical Importance of Addressing Chronic Absence in the Early Grades* (Attendance Works, 2018). It is important to distinguish between chronic absenteeism and truancy, which is missing school without permission (Attendance Works, 2018).

Incidence of Chronic Absence

In the 2015-16 school year, the incidence of chronic absence in the United States was greater than seven million students who missed more than 15 school days (U.S. Department of Education, 2016). These chronic absences resulted in over 100 million school days lost (US Department of Education, 2016). California students missed an average of 9.8 school days per year in 2018-19 (CDE, 2020).

Cost of Absences

Chronic absences can cost the student, district, and family in a variety of ways. California schools are funded on an attendance-centered system called Local Control Funding Formula, where schools receive a set amount of funding for each student who attends daily. Therefore, absent students reduce the funds available to the school site, jeopardizing school success and the future and causing financial harm to the learning community. The CDE reports that the ADA per student in grades 9-12 is \$9572 per 185-day school year or \$51.74 per day, resulting in a minimum of \$931 loss for every chronically absent student (CDE, 2022).

Academic Impact of Chronic Absenteeism

In addition to the fiscal cost of chronic absence, academic costs also exist for the student. Research shows students who are chronically absent students in kindergarten and first grade are less likely to attain grade-level reading by third grade and four times more likely to drop out of school (Attendance Works, 2018; Darnell et al., 2019; Gottfried, 2014; McKinley-Yoder, 2017). Gottfried (2014) performed a quasi-experimental study to investigate the effects of student absences on academic achievement. The author found that increased absence led to decreased standardized math and reading scores. In the Chicago Longitudinal Study (CLS), Smerillo et al. (2018) reported that 4th - 6th grade students with chronic absences had a greater math achievement gap in 8th grade. Further investigation into the CLS found that chronic absence in middle grades resulted in a reduced probability of high school graduation by 18% (Smerillo et al., 2018).

Employment Impact

The U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics (2021) reports that individuals without a high school diploma earn an average of \$619 per week compared to those with a diploma who earn \$781 per week. Unemployment rates are higher for individuals without a high school diploma at 11.7% compared to 9% of those with a high school diploma (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2021).

Socioemotional Impact

Social-emotional development influences a child's self-confidence, empathy, and ability to develop meaningful relationships (CDC, 2021). Chronically absent students suffer from socioemotional impacts in addition to academic impacts on their education. Gottfried's (2014) study investigated chronic absenteeism's effect on academic achievement and socioemotional outcomes and found that chronically absent students suffer from disengagement and alienation.

Elementary and middle school are the ages that social-emotional development is most affected by chronic absence through self-reported scores (Santibanez & Guarino, 2021). High school students report that social awareness, kindness, respect, empathy, and self-regulation, decrease as more days of school are missed; this is reported in a linear progression with a steeper rate of loss (Santibanez & Guarino, 2021).

Strategies to Address Absenteeism

A review of the literature reveals intervention tools that can be used by school districts, school nurses, and educators to help to decrease chronic absenteeism. There has been growing national attention regarding chronic absenteeism since the Every Student Succeeds Act of 2015. The Healthy Schools Campaign (HSC) has developed the Addressing the Health-Related Causes of Chronic Absence (AHRCCA) tool kit (HSC, 2022). This toolkit focuses on helping educators and school district decision-makers with information to address chronic absenteeism (HSC, 2022). The evidenced-based tool kit from AHRCCA focuses on the common causes of absenteeism. The tool kit addresses acting by collecting data, creating a plan and collaborating with community and health care partners to reduce the student's absences (HSC, 2022). This tool kit addresses access to school nurses based on the reason for the chronic absence, such as asthma, oral health and acute illness, but also discusses utilization of other school staff to address absences (HSC, 2022).

School nurses have developed evidence-based interventions to support decreasing illness-related chronic absences. Arimas-Macalino et al. (2019) used the Fade Quality Improvement (QI) process to decrease absences in her organization. Arimas-Macalino et al. (2019) reviewed attendance data of 9th and 10th grade students searching for students with chronic absenteeism and cluster related illness absences. A case review and analysis were completed for 26 students

which identified 11 students with chronic illnesses (Arimas-Macalino et al., 2019). This QI program demonstrated a need for a standardized process to identify and flag for illness-related absences and ultimately a chronic absence procedure algorithm (Arimas-Macalino et al., 2019). This algorithm allows for early identification of chronically ill students and standardizes the attendance monitoring process. Standardization of the attendance process promotes early identification, better educational outcomes, and improved student experiences (Gottfried, 2014; Rankine et al., 2021).

Munson Healthcare Charlevoix Hospital (MHCH) funded a school nurse program at nine local schools (Jacobsen et al., 2016). This program was funded through state and local grants plus funds from the hospital. The school nurses were able to tailor their own health programs based on the needs of the schools, and a few initiatives were instituted to include chronic absenteeism (Jacobsen et al., 2016). Through the work of the MHCH nurses at the nine school sites, chronic student absenteeism dropped from 27% in 2009-10 school year to 17% in 2013-14 school year, providing a good example of a sensitive outcome measure that validates the role of the school nurse (Jacobsen et al., 2016).

School Nurse-led Active Surveillance

A standardized evidence-based approach to addressing chronic absenteeism resulted in the NASN School Nurse-led Active Surveillance Manual. This school nurse-led surveillance manual will be implemented in the district of interest. The manual grew out of a review of the literature and knowledge that school nurses play an important role in decreasing and addressing chronic absenteeism (NASN, 2020b). This manual is an evidence-based practice (EBP) guideline with systematically developed strategies to help decrease chronic absenteeism that align with the nursing process and strategies to improve attendance (NASN, 2020b). The manual was reviewed

by experts in the field of school nursing and subsequently piloted by six school nurses in different states. The pilot nurses adopted the manual in their school nursing practice (NASN, 2020b). Implementing the NASN School Nurse-Led Active Surveillance Manual will help standardize the attendance process and improve attendance tracking for health-related absences. The manual is an eight-step approach based on the nursing process.

The manual addresses identification of reasons for a student absence including acute illness, chronic illness, concussions, and mental health conditions (NASN, 2020b). Research indicates that chronic absences are multifocal with health-related absences the leading contributor to chronic absences (Reed & Fothergill, 2017). Despite a student's absence being recorded as an illness, a process is not in place to alert the school nurse of the illness. Notification of an illness-related absence allows for a school nurse to collect and interpret important health information and allows for necessary interventions or accommodations as needed for student success (Arimas-Macalino et al., 2019; McKinley-Yoder, 2017; NASN, 2020b; Rankine et al., 2021).

Assessment

Nursing assessment systematically gathers health-related data that will lead to a nursing diagnosis (American Nurses Association [ANA], n.d.). School nurses assess the medical history of the chronically absent student as well as their psychological, socioeconomic, and lifestyle factors. Nurses use this systematic assessment to analyze the data regarding their patient and develop a nursing care plan (ANA, n.d). The assessment process assists the school nurse in planning and prioritizing care for the chronically absent student (McKinley-Yoder, 2017; Rankine et al., 2021; Schroder et al., 2021). The school nurse assessment aligns with NASN's Framework for 21st Century School Nursing Practice™ care coordination principle, and through

care coordination nurse develop plans to optimize student health and attendance (Rankine et al., 2021; NASN, 2020a).

Outreach

School nurses must have reliable procedures and access to attendance data to accurately identify students who are at risk for chronic absence. Arimas-Macilino et al. (2019) developed an effective standardized tracking tool to help to identify chronically absent students more easily through a QI project. The district of interest does not currently have a standardized process to identify students with chronic health-related absences. Implementation of the NASN School Nurse-Led Surveillance manual will help to identify students who are at risk due to chronic health-related absences.

Methods

The purpose of this project is to develop and implement a process to consistently identify students who have health-related chronic absences, notify school nurses of students who have health-related chronic absences for follow-up using the NASN School Nurse-Led Active Surveillance Manual, and document and evaluate effectiveness of school nurse intervention. Through application of the Iowa Model and NASN Framework for 21st Century School Nursing PracticeTM, attendance processes, policies, and data in the district of interest will be analyzed. Table 1 s the timeline the school nurse purposes for this DNP project (Appendix A; Table 1).

Setting

The project will take place in a southern California school district on the western edge of Los Angeles County. The pilot will occur at one district high school with approximately 1,800 students in ninth to twelfth grade.

Participants

Participants for this project will include the school site level principal, site attendance clerk, site health clerk, and the school nurse, the principal investigator. These participants will play an essential role in implementing this project as they have the working knowledge regarding the site-level attendance procedures. The district data specialist will also be included in the project as the expert at gathering attendance data from the Student Information System (SIS) and providing background for past attendance procedures. The Assistant Superintendent of Educational Services will serve as the district-level policy expert. Students and their families will participate in this project through the outreach of the school nurse.

Ethical Considerations

An Institutional Review Board (IRB) application will be submitted to California State University, Fullerton (Append I; Figure 5). A letter of permission to complete the project in the district of interest will be obtained before starting this project (Appendix J; Figure 6).

A review of attendance data poses no more than minimal risks to students; therefore, no ethical concerns were identified. Parental consent is not required as attendance tracking is a state-mandated process and care coordination by school nurses is a standard of practice.

Operational Definitions

Illness absences are reported for illness or a health-related appointment (i.e., doctor's visit, mental health, or dental). Chronic absenteeism is defined as a student who misses more than 10% of the school year or more than two days per month, as most school months have 20 to 21 days of monthly attendance (Attendance Works, 2018; Rankine et al., 2021; Schroder et al., 2021). Clustered health-related absences are defined as missing four or more consecutive school days due to an illness-related absence (Arimas-Macalino et al., 2019). For this project, the school nurse will evaluate and develop interventions for students who have clustered health-related absences.

Design and Pilot the Practice Change

The School Nurse-Led Active Surveillance Manual is an eight-step process that will help guide the process to consistently identifying students with health-related chronic absenteeism and ensure referral to the school nurse. Implementation of steps one and two, within the manual, will aid in identification of students with chronic absenteeism and students who are missing school for health-related reasons.

Step 1: Identify Chronically Absent Students

The active surveillance process begins with identifying the current attendance tracking process. The school nurse will examine district policies, data entry processes, absence category definitions, and attendance clerk training to better understand the current attendance tracking process.

Step 2: Identify Chronically Absent Students for Health Reasons

Current practice does not allow for consistent referral to the school nurse when a student has multiple health-related absences. Utilizing the chronic absence definition within The School Nurse-Led Active Surveillance Manual, attendance clerks will notify the school nurse of all students who miss four or more days in a month consecutively for health-related reasons. The school nurse and district data specialist will develop a tracking query through the SIS to help identify students who have missed more than four consecutive days for health-related absences and a synopsis of previous attendance history for identified students.

Verify Preferences and Constraints

Currently, the school nurse is not able to implement additional steps in the School Nurse-Led Active Surveillance Manual due to lack of notification to the nurse for students with health-related chronic absences. With the assistance of the site and district team, the group will determine current procedures, and identify underlying gaps in the process for identification of health-related chronic absences.

Understanding Current Processes

The school nurse will develop a flow chart to determine the current attendance tracking processes and identify the gaps in the process. This flow chart will be developed and compared to the best practice NASN attendance triage flow chart (Appendix G; Figure 3), helping the

school nurse determine areas of weakness in district process. NASN attendance triage flow chart addresses attendance follow-up process for students who are identified as chronically absent to include referral to nurse for students with health-related absences. Ending with intervention and evaluation by nurse to assist in attendance improvement. The team will examine current district attendance policies, investigate current attendance tracking and data entry processes, and standardize absence category definitions.

Develop Localized Protocol and Implementation Plan

Developing and implementing a protocol for consistent identification and referral to the school nurse will be created with team buy-in through brainstorming. The team will meet to participate in a brainstorming activity to determine possible causes for and identify gaps in current practice. They will identify the underlying causes for the lack of a standardized process, for identification and notification of health-related chronic absences and generate possible strategies for improvements.

Plan for Implementation

These strategies will be developed into a formal protocol to implement at the pilot high school. This protocol will include district attendance policies, data entry processes, and standardization of absence category definitions. A referral process will be developed for use by attendance clerk and health clerk for referral to school nurse. The school nurse will develop a standardized documentation process to include mode of outreach with family or student, interventions to be implemented, and evaluation of the intervention effectiveness. All nursing documentation will be in the SIS. This protocol will be disseminated to the pilot high school and reviewed with each site-level team member before implementation.

Create an Evaluation Plan

Evaluation of this project will include recording the number of students marked ill before and after the project's intervention. The number of students referred to the nurse for health-related chronic absences and feasibility of implementing the project district-wide will also be measured.

Measures

All data will be extracted from the SIS, which contains attendance records for approximately 1,800 students. The school nurse will be responsible for documenting interventions, outcomes, and outreach to families within the medical notes section of the SIS.

Identification and Referral to School Nurse

The school nurse will measure the accuracy of the attendance recording by the attendance clerk. This will be assessed through conversation with the attendance clerk to review criteria for identifying student's absence as illness. The principal investigator will also assess the attendance clerks understanding of referral process for students with cluster health-related absences. This will be evaluated every two weeks for the duration of the project. Frequent check ins with attendance clerk will allow for redirection and reevaluation as needed.

Follow-up and Effectiveness of Intervention

The literature shows that when school nurses intervene in student health care, the student has improved attendance and is less likely to leave school early due to illness or injury (Rankine et al., 2021; Schroeder et al., 2018; Weismuller et al., 2007). Through case management, the school nurse will follow the student, document the effectiveness of interventions, and determine improvement in attendance and health outcomes. If the student absences are not improved, the school nurse will reevaluate the individualized health care plan and follow up with family to

identify needed changes to interventions or need for additional referrals. If the school nurse is not able to identify ways to decrease student absenteeism, a referral to school administration will be initiated.

The school nurse will measure the number of students referred to the school nurse with cluster health-related absences, the number of students provided with follow-up and intervention, and the type of intervention provided. At the end of the pilot period, the number of students with cluster health-related absences will be collected and compared to students who received school nurse follow-up and intervention to determine if students with intervention had improved attendance. Based on the literature, it is hypothesized that school nurse intervention would lead to decreased health-related absences.

Program Effectiveness and Sustainability

Overall success of the project will be measured by identifying students with clustered health-related absences, who have been referred to school nurse and have decreased absenteeism resulting from school nurse intervention. Baseline data from the 2019-20 school year will be collected to determine the number of students with cluster health-related absences prior to piloting this project. This data will be compared to same time frame from the 2022-23 school year to measure the effectiveness of school nurse intervention after referral for cluster health-related absences using the NASN School Nurse-Led Active Surveillance Manual. Comparison of the two school years will help the project investigator understand how many students with cluster health-related absences could have received followed-up by school nurse and will show missed opportunities for school nurse intervention.

Sustainability

To understand the feasibility of district-wide implementation with current school nurse staffing, the principal investigator will measure the feasibility of implementing the pilot project district-wide by comparing the total number of students referred to the school nurse with cluster health-related absences compared to the total number of students the school nurse was able to initiate follow-up with after referral. If it is a sustainable process, the protocol will be disseminated to all school sites with training for attendance clerks at the beginning of each school year or upon hire. School nurses will be trained on the protocol, use of the School Nurse-Led Surveillance Manual, intervention, and documentation tool. Evaluation data will be collected at the end of each semester to assess the impact of school nurse intervention on cluster health-related absences.

Results

Data related to the number students who had four and greater cluster health-related absences for the first semester of the 2019-2020 school year, August- January was collected and compared to the same time frame for the 2022-2023 school year. In the 2019-2020 school year, 165 students had four and greater cluster health-related absences (Appendix B; Table 2). Of the 165 students who missed four and greater cluster health-related absences, only four were referred to the school nurse (Appendix C; Table 2). In the 2022-2023 school year, 300 students had four and greater cluster health-related absences, and 60 were referred to the school nurse.

Of those 300 students, 71 were absent for COVID-related illness and were provided with COVID quarantine guidance in line with county guidelines. Of the remaining 229 students, 147 were documented as Illness (I) and 82 as Other (O) for their cluster health-related absence. Of the 82 coded as O, nine were absent for family reasons or college visits and were not eligible for referral to the school nurse despite having met the criteria of four and greater cluster health-related absences. After accounting for COVID illness and students not eligible for referral, 220 students met the criteria for referral to the school nurse during the first semester of the 2022-2023 school year.

Sixty of the 220 students were eligible for referral to the school nurse for I and O absence reasons were referred (Appendix D; Table 3). For ten of those 60 students, an SST, 504, or IEP meeting was convened. Of the 50 remaining students, 21 families were contacted via phone, and 29 were contacted via email by the school nurse to discuss health status, attendance and to assess the need for interventions.

Discussion

School nurses are the trusted health experts with the school community who help plan and implement actions to increase attendance for identified students (Schroder et al., 2018). When school nurses intervene in the healthcare of students, it can result in improved attendance and decreases the likelihood of students leaving school early due to illness or injury (Rankine et al., 2021; Schroder et al., 2018; Weismuller et al., 2007). Through care coordination for acute and chronic health conditions, school nurses identify those students who are at greatest risk for chronic absenteeism (Darnell et al., 2019; NASN, 2021; Paulson et al., 2021; Schroder et al., 2021).

Mechanisms for Tracking Student Absences

To consistently identify students with health-related chronic absences, the PI worked with district and school site-level staff to determine the current attendance training and tracking processes. The PI and site-level attendance clerk discussed the definition and use of the various attendance codes available in the SIS.

District Attendance Manual Code Definitions:

- I = Illness. Used when the parent or guardian reports the student ill, injured, or other medical-related reasons (e.g., medical appointments, COVID, cold symptoms.).
- O = Other. Used for any other personal justifiable and other excused absence (e.g., medical note for illnesses of four or more days, college visits, or family reasons, such as funeral)

Identifying Chronically Absent Students

Standardized Operating Procedure and Flow Chart Development

A standardized operating procedure (SOP) was developed in conjunction with the team of stakeholders, including the attendance clerk, health clerk, school nurse and district-level data specialist (Appendix H; Figure 4). The SOP served as a guide for attendance clerks, health clerks, and school nurses to identify, manage, refer, and document intervention for students with cluster health-related absences. The SOP includes absence category definitions from district of interest existing attendance manual to ensure a consistent recording process for the attendance clerk. The SOP outlines the referral process to the school nurse. The SOP guides the school nurse in steps for outreach, intervention, documentation, and reassessment for the student with cluster health-related absences. The SOP and flow chart were reviewed by Assistant Superintendent of Education Services, site principal, attendance clerk, and a school nurse.

A flow chart modeled after the NASN Triage flow chart was also developed. The flow chart was modified to indicate that the attendance clerk would notify the school nurse when a student missed four and greater cluster health-related absences upon occurrence, versus a monthly report as suggested by the NASN Triage Flowsheet (Appendix G, Figure 3). Research shows that communicating with parents and guardians when a student is absent helps reduce student absences regardless of the absence (Rogers et al., 2017). Initiating contact earlier increases the chances the student will return to the classroom sooner.

Implementing the SOP and Flow Chart

The SOP and flow chart identified the steps the attendance clerk, health clerk, and school nurse should take when a student was to be referred for cluster health-related absences. After developing the SOP and flow chart, the PI reviewed the SOP and flow chart with the attendance

clerk and health clerk in a face-to-face session. The PI answered all clarifying questions from the attendance clerk and health clerk. At the end of the first month, the PI used the absence query from the SIS to determine the number of students who had missed four or more cluster health-related absences and compared it to the number of students referred to the school nurse during that month. Upon noting that eligible students were not referred to the school nurse, the PI queried the attendance and health clerks to better understand the reasons for the discrepancy between the number of students eligible for referral and those referred. The PI reinforced the SOP and flow chart information, including the eligibility criteria for referral to the school nurse, and confirmed understanding.

After a second month of identifying students, the PI used the consecutive absence query from the SIS to compare the number of eligible students to the number of students referred and noted similar trends in the number of students referred to the school nurse. It was determined that the flow chart was not utilized by the attendance and health clerks, who reported that it felt more aligned with school nurse duties than with clerk roles.

At the end of the data collection period, the Assistant Superintendent of Education Services left the school district, and the Assistant Superintendent of Student Services became a member of the district-level team. The PI reviewed the SOP with the Assistant Superintendent of Student Services. It was agreed that using the 'O' code for students who brought a medical increased confusion regarding the student's reason for absence. This practice will be addressed when attendance clerks receive their annual training next school year. An SOP and retraining will help ensure accurate attendance data tracking.

Outreach and Planning

Case management by the school nurse is a proactive strategy within the NASN Framework that addresses health and academic goals (NASN, 2021). Case management is collaborative and continuous process involving the student's family, community health providers, and school health team leading to coordination of school health services that achieve individual health and educational goals (NASN, 2021). The school nurse began the case management process for 50 of the referred students by reaching out to parents or guardians of referred students through either a phone call or email. Using the information provided by parents, an assessment of the student's status and ability to return to school was determined. If further information was required from a community health provider, the PI requested either documentation or permission to speak with the provider. After assessing the student's ability to return to campus, a plan of care was developed, implemented, and discussed with student's family. The plan of care was disseminated to school staff, including teachers, health clerk, counselors, and assistant principals as needed. Through case management, the PI continued to follow up with student and family to assess if interventions were effective. The student referral, assessment, planning, intervention, and communication with school staff were documented in the SIS.

For ten referred students, the PI addressed cluster health-related absences during either an SST, 504, or IEP meeting. The PI attended three SST meetings for students with cluster health-related absences. These meetings allowed the PI to begin the case management process and develop and implement a plan of care for the student. For three students, it was noted an IEP meeting was scheduled within the next 30 days. Before the IEP meeting, the PI contacted the student's family, began the assessment process, and requested an invite to the IEP meeting from

the IEP case manager. Only one of these students required adjustments to their IEP accommodations to help improve access to campus and education. The other two students the PI was able to continue the case management and follow-up process with families as both students had no more cluster health-related absences. The PI attended four 504 scheduled meetings of students with cluster health-related absences. These students were already on the PI case management load. At these meetings, reassessment and adjustment of plan of care was implemented. These interventions for all ten students were documented in the meeting record and SIS. As needed, the school nurse informed teachers and school staff of needed accommodations or changes to previous plan of care. The PI will continue to monitor all ten students through the case management process.

Parents and guardians of 160 students who qualified for referral but were not referred were sent an email from the attendance clerk bringing awareness to the four or more-cluster health-related absences. This email contained contact information for the school nurse informing families to reach out to the school nurse if the parent believed planning was required to return their student to campus or if they needed obtaining health care.

COVID illnesses were reported with illness code. To differentiate COVID illness from other illnesses, the attendance clerk entered a note which indicated these students had tested positive for COVID and were referred to the school nurse for quarantine guidance. All students whose families reported a positive COVID test received a quarantine notice via email instructing the family of the county quarantine guidelines.

Interpretation of the Data

Overall, there was an increased number of referrals to the school nurse from the 2019-2020 school year to the 2022-2023 school year. This increase in the number of students referred

was largely due to having brought attention to the students with cluster health-related absences, engaging the attendance clerk, and implementing a referral process. By highlighting these students, their cluster health-related absences became known to the school nurse, who could reach out to families.

Despite increased referrals for the 2022-2023 school year, many more students were not referred despite meeting the criteria. One of the main problems is with the coding of absences and the use of the 'O' code. Based on past practice, the attendance clerk used the 'O' code for students who provided a medical note to excuse their absence. Often, the code was first 'I' and then was changed to 'O' upon receipt of the medical note. It is unclear whether the attendance clerk believed the medical note was a replacement for referral to the school nurse or absence coding led to confusion regarding the need for referral. The PI was unable to determine if there was a breakdown in communication, lack of understanding, or adherence to past practices that led to the attendance clerk not referring all eligible students. This is an opportunity to continue reinforcing the referral criteria and promote an accurate attendance-taking processes and a deeper examination of the definitions and uses of the attendance codes.

Based on the findings from the data collection period, the PI revised the SOP to clarify the attendance codes to increase consistency of attendance tracking and referral to school nurses. In following the NASN School Nurse-Led Active Surveillance Manual, all students meeting the criteria should be referred to the school nurse. The PI reviewed the SOP with the Assistant Superintendent of Student Services, a new member of the team. It was agreed that using the 'O' code for students who brought a medical note increased confusion regarding the student's reason for absence. This practice will be addressed when attendance clerks receive their annual training next school year. An SOP and retraining will help ensure accurate attendance data tracking.

Sustainability

An automated email distribution system for all students with four consecutive days of health-related illness would increase the ability to sustain the program at each school site. With the assistance of the health clerk to make an initial inquiry to parents or guardians regarding student's absence, a triage system could be implemented and ensure all students who meet the criteria for referral are contacted. The district of interest has increased the attendance surveillance for chronically absent students, which will help to sustain the school nurse-led intervention.

For the school nurse to sustain tracking a high number of students to track and case manage, a tracking system will need to be put into place. The PI recommends utilizing a form like the NASN Chronic Conditions Tracking form from A Model for School Nurse-Led Case Management (NASN, 2021). Utilizing this tracking method will help the school nurse to accurately track and monitor students with cluster health-related absences. The data collected on the tracking form could be utilized to inform the district of interest about the school nurses increased caseload and student acuity in the district. Giving this information to the administrative team would help make the case to increase the number of school nurses within the school district. Increased staffing would increase the ability to monitor cluster health-related absences and increase ADA for the school district.

Recommendations

Consistency and Improved Tracking

The use of the 'O' code for students who provide a medical note after having missed four days for a health-related absence should be eliminated. Instead, an absence of this type should be marked with an 'I' to allow for accuracy in tracking and identifying students who meet the

criteria to be referred to the school nurse and to accurately indicate that a student was ill. After consultation with the Assistant Superintendent of Student Services, a plan was developed to eliminate this practice in future years.

Improve Outreach and Case Management

Due to many students meeting the criteria for referral to the school nurse, a triage system should be implemented to assist the school nurse in identifying students in need of further follow-up and intervention. This process could be facilitated by developing a standardized tool that could be used by non-licensed assistive staff, such as the health clerk, to interview the family to help determine the urgency for school nurse follow-up. The current process includes an email sent to the parent or guardians from the attendance office after the student has missed three days for illness-related reasons to request a note from a provider. This email could be modified to provide contact information for the school nurse and remind families that the school nurse is available to help support student return.

According to A Model for School Nurse-Led Case Management (NASN, 2021), the case management process can be used for students with attendance and helps prioritize those with barriers to health and academic success. Utilizing the school nurse-led attendance tracking in conjunction with case management, the school nurse can prioritize which students and families have a higher priority for contacting. Improved case management will improve student health outcomes, attendance, academic success, and support families (NANS, 2021).

Strengths/Limitations

There are many strengths in this project. As the project unfolded, the school district focused more on attendance. This allowed the PI to share the School Nurse-Led Active Surveillance Model with many in the leadership team and other school nurses within the school district. This

helped to increase the support from leadership and begin a larger dialog for the upcoming school year.

Limitations to the project included data collected for was only ninth through twelfth-grade students in a single affluent high school. These findings may not apply to lower grade levels. The pilot high school is in an affluent area of Los Angeles County, and most students have access to care, resulting in an increased number of students who sought care on day four or five of absence.

An unexpected limitation of the project was a change in district stakeholders. The Assistant Superintendent of Educational Services resigned in January, resulting in an administrative void within the initial team. In February, the district appointed the Direct of Pupil Services to Assistant Superintendent of Student Services overseeing attendance processes. The PI needed to bring the new Assistant Superintendent up to speed on the PI project. The new Assistant Superintendent was not a part of the initial planning process but is in line with the importance of tracking chronic health-related absences.

Implications for School Nursing Practice

School nurses are the trusted health professional within the education community. Students with direct access to school nurses have increased health and educational outcomes such as increased attendance, higher test scores, and fewer adult chronic health conditions (NASN, 2021). Case management for students with chronic health-related absences can lead to increased attendance, which can help students achieve optimal health and academic success (NASN, 2021).

During the pandemic, schools were not as focused on the number of days students missed for health-related reasons. Now that schools have more or less returned to normal, schools are

taking note of and focused on students with increased absences. When the school nurse is involved in the attendance process, students can return to school quicker. The school nurse is best able to give parents accurate information regarding when a student can return to campus following an illness or other health conditions as part of the outreach and case management process. As previously mentioned, school nurse-led case management involves a nursing assessment, nursing judgment, development of a plan of care, implementation, and evaluation of the student with cluster health-related absences. The plan developed by the school nurse helps the student to return to campus and promote academic success.

Conclusion

School nurses are essential to the school team as they bridge the gap between health care and the learning environment. Despite being underutilized in their area of expertise, through the implementation of the School Nurse-Led Attendance Manual, the school nurse is better able to identify students who are chronically absent for health-related reasons. As the school nurse addresses the needs of the chronically absent student, they are also addressing the SDOH and increasing the likelihood of future student success by ensuring the student has access to their education, leading to future health and wealth attainment.

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Appendix A

Table 1

Timeline

Timing	Activities	Responsible Person	Where
July	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop flow chart of attendance procedures • Compare flow chart to NASN flow chart • Send invite to team for brainstorming 	School nurse	District office
August	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brainstorming session with team • Complete driver diagram • Develop protocol • Disseminate protocol to pilot site 	Entire team	District office
September	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement protocol • Track data every two weeks • Initiate referrals • Outreach to families 	Site team School nurse	Pilot high school
October	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Track data every two weeks • Initiate referrals • Outreach to families 	Site team School nurse	Pilot high school
November	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Track data every two weeks • Initiate referrals • Outreach to families 	Site team School nurse	Pilot high school
December	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Track data every two weeks • Initiate referrals • Outreach to families 	Site team School nurse	Pilot high school
January	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review data • Analyze data 	School nurse Site principal Assistant Sup of Student Services	District office

Appendix B

Table 2

2019-2020 Students with Cluster Health-Related Absences and Number of Students Referred to School Nurse

Number of Student with Cluster Health-Related Absences	165 Students
Number of Student Referred to School Nurse	4 Students

Appendix C

Table 3

2022-2023 Students with Cluster Health-Related Absences and Number of Students Referred to School Nurse

Number of Student with Cluster Health-Related Absences	300 students
Number of Students with Cluster Health-Related Absences marked COVID	71 students
Number of Students with Cluster Health-Related Absences marked Illness	147 students
Number of Students with Cluster Health-Related Absences marked Other	82 students
Number of Students with Cluster Absences marked Other, not eligible for referral	9 students
Number of Students Eligible for Referral	220 students
Total Student Referred	60 students

Appendix D

Table 4

2022-2023 Disposition of Referred Students

Total Student Referred	60 students
Contact via SST/IEP or 504 Meetings	10 students
Contact via Phone	21 students
Contact via Email	29 students

Appendix E

Figure 1

The Iowa Model Revised

Appendix F

Figure 2

Framework for 21st Century School Nursing Practice™

Appendix G

Figure 3
Triage Flowsheet

TRIAGE FLOWSHEET

Special thanks to R. McClanahan for initial development of this algorithm for the manual.

Appendix H

Figure 4

Standard Operating Procedure

Task	Health-Related Attendance Tracking Procedure
Written by	Melissa Foster, District School Nurse, Health Services Dept Chair
Date Written	January 2023
Team Members Involved	District School Nurses (SN), Health Clerks, Licensed Vocational Nurses, Attendance Clerks, Principals, Teachers
<p>Purpose</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assure the accurate documentation, tracking, reporting, and follow-up for students with cluster health-related absences and identify students who may be at higher risk of illness or injury to provide additional support or accommodations that allow them to return to school • <p>Definitions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clustered health-related absences are defined as missing four or more consecutive school days due to an illness related absence. <p>Legal Reference</p> <p>California Education Code 48205 establishes a legal requirement for students to attend school every day, allowing student absences to be excused for religious holidays, bereavement, quarantine, illness, medical appointments, or court appearances (California Legislative Information, 2022).</p> <p>Absence Documentation Procedure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teacher marks student absence and absence appear as “A” in Aeries. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parent completes online attendance form for school site citing reason for absence. • Based on reason given by parent, attendance clerk will code absence as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Illness (I): excused absence for illness or injury for medical reason per parent report • Other (O): Personal, justifiable, and other excused absences (bereavement and court appearances) per EC 48205 • Unverified (A): Absence is initially recorded as unverified, when marked absent by teacher, until the reason for the absence can be verified by the attendance clerk and absence code changed. • Tardy (T): Tardy to class less than 30 minutes • Activity (V): School activity under the control and supervision of credentialed employees on a school day during school hours • Truant (Y or Z): Student who violates the compulsory ed (truancy) law. 	

- Religious (R): Used to describe an absence due to a religious holiday or religious retreat.

Tracking, Referral, and Monitoring by Attendance Clerks

- Attendance Clerk will run consecutive absence report, bimonthly, for students with four or more cluster health-related absences and refer identified students to the school nurse and health clerk within 24 hrs.
- As daily attendance is reviewed, Attendance clerk can refer students with consecutive health-related absences to health clerk and school nurse.
- Referral will be made via email, include the following information: Student name, Birthdate, Grade, Dates Absent, Absence reason given by parent.
- Continue to monitor identified students' attendance for more days missed or future cluster health-related absences.

Outreach and Monitoring by School Nurse and Health Clerks

- Health clerk will review the list of students on the report to determine which students have higher priority for referral to the school nurse.
- Referral timeline:
 - Students with medical history noted in SIS will be referred to SN within 24 hours
 - Students with communicable illness will be referred to SN within 24 hours
 - Students with report of concussion will be referred to SN within 24 hours
 - Students with general report of illness and no medical history noted in SIS will be referred to SN within 48 hours
 - Students with general report of illness and medical note will be referred to SN within 48 hours. Health clerk will review the list of students and identify students with known chronic health problems. School Nurse will review attendance and health data in SIS
- School Nurse will outreach to families via phone or email to further identify health-related reasons for absence and review student's health history and make assessment of student status and ability to return to campus.
- School Nurses will develop a nursing diagnosis and plan with family for students to return to school. Refer to school nurse-led surveillance of chronic absenteeism for further guidance.
- School Nurse will document contact and plan in SIS under the student's medical notes and upload any developed plans to student documents in SIS
- School Nurse and Health Clerk will continue to monitor identified students' attendance for more days missed or future cluster health-related absences.

Notification of Administrators and Teachers

- School nurse will notify teachers via email of health care plans or classroom accommodations needed.
- School nurse will upload healthcare plan to SIS in student documents section.

- School nurse will ensure site administrator is aware of contact with families for cluster health-related absences.

Reference:

National Association of School Nurses (NASN). (2020b). *School nurse-led surveillance of chronic absenteeism*. NASN.

Appendix I

Figure 5

IRB Letter of Withdraw

[External] HSR-22-23-1 - Admin Withdrawal: Admin Withdrawal - IRB Approval Not Required

do-not-reply@cayuse.com <do-not-reply@cayuse.com>

Fri 7/29/2022 1:28 PM

To: Foster, Melissa <melissa.foster@csu.fullerton.edu>;rmcclanahan@fullerton.edu
<rmcclanahan@fullerton.edu>

Cc: IRB <irb@fullerton.edu>

External Email Use Caution and Confirm Sender

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, FULLERTON

Office of Research and Sponsored Projects

P.O. Box 6850 or 1121 N. State College Blvd., 2nd Fl., Fullerton, CA 92831 / T 657-278-7719 / F 657-278-7238

WITHDRAWAL NOTICE

*From the Institutional Review Board
California State University, Fullerton*

July 29, 2022

PI: Melissa Foster

Application No. HSR-22-23-1

Study Title: School Nurse-Led Intervention for Health-Related Chronic Absenteeism

This email is to notify you that the above-referenced has been withdrawn by the Office of Research Compliance. Based on the information provided, this protocol does not require IRB approval. The file is being closed because of this notification.

If you have any questions regarding this matter please contact the IRB office at irb@fullerton.edu.

Cc: IRB Office

Rachel McClanahan

Appendix J

Figure 6

Letter of Support

Las Virgenes Unified School District

4111 Las Virgenes Road, Calabasas, CA 91302
(818) 880-4000 • Fax (818) 880-4200
<http://lvusd.org>

May 18, 2022

California State University, Fullerton
800 N State College Blvd.
Fullerton, CA 92831

To Whom It May Concern,

Please accept this letter of support for Ms. Melissa Foster. Ms. Foster will be engaging with Las Virgenes Unified in her doctoral project entitled, School Nurse-Led Intervention for Health-Related Chronic Absenteeism. Ms. Foster has permission to access the attendance and health data for our students from the period of May, 2022 - May, 2023.

Please do not hesitate to reach out to my office if you have additional questions or if we can be of further support to Ms. Foster.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in purple ink that reads "Clara A. Finneran".

Clara A. Finneran, Ed.D
Assistant Superintendent, Education